

Comparative Analysis of Neutronic and Energy Group Structures for Soluble Boron and D₂O/H₂O Moderators in SMR Assemblies

Youngrok Lee¹, Donghwan Park², Joo-il Yoon³ and Hyun Chul Lee^{1*}

¹School of Mechanical Engineering, Pusan National University, 2, Busandaehak-ro 63beon-gil, Geumjeong-gu, Busan, 46241, Republic of Korea

²Central Research Institute, Korea Hydro & Nuclear Power Co., Ltd, 70, Yuseong-daero 1312beon-gil, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, 34101, Republic of Korea

³Nuclear Power Plant Engineering Department, KEPCO International Nuclear Graduate School, 658-91 Haemaji-ro, Seosang-myeon, Ulju-gun, 45014, Ulsan, Republic of Korea

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803636

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the feasibility of employing a D₂O/H₂O mixed moderator for spectral shift-based reactivity control as an alternative to soluble boron in the design of soluble boron-free (SBF) small modular reactors (SMRs). While SBF operation aims to manage excess reactivity through advanced BAs, control rod insertion remains necessary during operation. In this context, spectral shift control is explored as a supplementary strategy for reactivity management. A typical two-dimensional fuel assembly of an SBF core is analyzed under three moderator conditions: pure H₂O, soluble boron in H₂O, and D₂O/H₂O mixture. Neutronic characteristics are evaluated using the four-factor formula. Results show that the D₂O/H₂O mixed moderator induces a significantly hardened neutron spectrum with lower absorption, thereby increasing the fast fission factor and thermal neutron utilization factor, which in turn contributes to an extended critical operation period compared to other cases. Additionally, a coarse-group energy structure optimization is performed using a modified reference method. The results indicate that the presence of a hardened spectrum necessitates a finer group structure to accurately preserve reaction rates.

Keywords: D₂O/H₂O moderator, neutron spectrum, SBF, SMR, MCS

1. INTRODUCTION

Unlike conventional pressurized water reactors (PWRs), which control reactivity using soluble boron as a neutron absorber, spectral shift control reactors (SSCRs) manage reactivity by shifting the neutron spectrum. One of the SSCR concepts involves the use of a mixed moderator composed of heavy water (D₂O) and light water (H₂O), which was first proposed in the 1960s [1], and later demonstrated to be viable through a series of experiments [2]. Subsequent studies have explored the adaptation of this concept to small modular reactors (SMRs) [3]. In this design, a higher ratio of D₂O is used at the beginning of the fuel cycle to produce a harder neutron spectrum. As the fuel depletes, the D₂O concentration is gradually reduced, which induces a neutron spectrum shift, thereby enabling sustained reactivity control throughout the cycle.

Recently, the development of PWR-based SMRs has been active, several designs emphasizing soluble boron-free (SBF) and long-cycle operation as key design requirements [4]. The core strategy in implementing SBF operation is to enhance the use of burnable absorbers (BAs) by developing innovative types incorporating high-concentration Gd₂O₃ [5]. These BAs are designed to manage the high excess reactivity present at the beginning of the cycle and to delay their depletion.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: hyunchul.lee@pusan.ac.kr (Hyun Chul Lee).

However, the stability of Gd₂O₃ under high-temperature and high-flux neutron irradiation remains a concern. Furthermore, even with the application of innovative BAs, a considerable amount of excess reactivity persists, making control rod insertion during operation practically unavoidable. Given these challenges, spectral shift reactivity control presents a promising alternative for reducing dependence on both advanced BAs and active control rod operation.

When a D₂O/H₂O mixed moderator is employed, the resulting neutron spectrum becomes significantly harder than that of a conventional PWR. This spectral hardening leads to notable differences in neutronic characteristics compared to those of conventional H₂O moderated systems. In the first part of this study, the neutronic characteristics of the D₂O/H₂O moderator system are investigated and compared with conventional H₂O and soluble boron moderator environments.

In conventional two-step reactor analysis methods for PWRs using deterministic codes, fine-group cross-sections are collapsed into two coarse group through flux-weighted averaging to preserve reaction rates. However, in systems with significantly hardened neutron spectra, this two-group energy structure can introduce substantial errors. Therefore, in the second part of this study, an optimized coarse energy group structure is sought to achieve comparable accuracy to the conventional PWR group structure when applied to the D₂O/H₂O moderated systems.

For this analysis, a two-dimensional fuel assembly model representative of an SBF reactor using conventional burnable absorbers is studied. Neutronic calculations are performed using the Monte Carlo continuous-energy neutron transport code MCS, developed at Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology [6]. The results are evaluated based solely on the infinite multiplication factor (k_{∞}), without explicitly accounting for neutron leakage.

2. COMPARATIVE NEUTRONIC STUDY

The SBF reactor employs a conventional 17×17 fuel assembly design. Figure 1 illustrates the geometric configurations of three representative assembly types, consistently modeled using 4 wt% enriched UO₂ fuel and integral gadolinia burnable absorbers containing 8 wt% Gd₂O₃ mixed with 2.5 wt% enriched UO₂ to ensure a uniform basis for comparison [5].

Figure 1. Typical 2D assembly configurations with BAs.

Figure 2 compares the neutron spectra of the 20 BA fuel assembly under three moderator conditions: pure H₂O, 2000 ppm soluble boron in H₂O, and a 50% D₂O concentration mixture. Compared to the pure H₂O case, the soluble boron case exhibits a slightly hardened spectrum due to thermal neutron absorption by boron, while the D₂O/H₂O mixture results in a significantly more hardened spectrum, attributed to the lower slowing-down power of D₂O.

Figure 2. Comparison of neutron spectra under different moderator conditions.

2.1. Burnup Analysis

Figure 3 presents the depletion calculation results of the 20 BA fuel assembly under three different moderator conditions. In (a), k_{∞} is shown as a function of burnup for the pure H₂O moderator case without any reactivity control. The cycle length is approximately 35 MWd/kgU, and BAs are mostly depleted by around 15 MWd/kgU. In (b), the critical boron concentration and critical D₂O volume fraction required to maintain criticality are plotted as functions of burnup for the soluble boron and D₂O/H₂O moderator cases, respectively. With soluble boron control, criticality is sustained slightly beyond 36 MWd/kgU, whereas the D₂O/H₂O moderator extends critical operation to approximately 43 MWd/kgU. In addition, the BAs exhibit slower depletion in the D₂O/H₂O case due to the hardened neutron spectrum, which also reduces their reactivity suppression effect.

Figure 3. Depletion calculation results of the fuel assembly: (a) k_{∞} as a function of burnup for the pure H₂O moderator case; (b) critical boron concentration and critical D₂O volume fraction for soluble boron and D₂O/H₂O moderator cases.

2.2. Four Factor Analysis

The four-factor formula was employed to analyze the neutronic characteristics for the 20 BA fuel assembly under three different moderator conditions. The four factors include the fast fission factor (ϵ), resonance escape probability (p), thermal utilization factor (f), and reproduction factor (η). Each case

was analyzed using a two-group energy structure with the group boundary set at 0.625 eV. The four-factor parameters were then computed using the two-group reaction rates as follows:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\nu\Sigma_{f1}\phi_1 + \nu\Sigma_{f2}\phi_2}{\nu\Sigma_{f2}\phi_2}, p = \frac{\Sigma_{s21}\phi_1}{\Sigma_{a1}\phi_1 + \Sigma_{s,21}\phi_1}, f = \frac{\Sigma_{a2}^F\phi_2}{\Sigma_{a2}\phi_2}, \eta = \frac{\nu\Sigma_{f2}\phi_2}{\Sigma_{a2}^F\phi_2}, \quad (1)$$

where $\nu\Sigma_{f1}\phi_1$ and $\nu\Sigma_{f2}\phi_2$ denote neutron production rates by fast and thermal fission, respectively. $\Sigma_{a1}\phi_1$ and $\Sigma_{a2}\phi_2$ represent the fast and thermal neutron absorption rates, $\Sigma_{a2}^F\phi_2$ indicates thermal neutron absorption rate by the fuel, and $\Sigma_{s21}\phi_1$ denotes thermal neutron production rate due to the slowing down of fast neutrons.

Table I summarizes the four-factors for a fresh fuel assembly under three moderator conditions. Both the soluble boron and D₂O/H₂O moderator cases maintain criticality, whereas the pure H₂O moderator is in a supercritical state.

Soluble boron control induces slight spectral hardening, which marginally increases ε . However, due to boron's high thermal neutron absorption cross-section, a lower f was obtained. while η and p remains nearly unchanged compared to the pure H₂O case.

In contrast, the D₂O/H₂O mixture significantly hardens the neutron spectrum, resulting in a higher ε . The lower slowing-down power of the mixed moderator results in reduced p . Slightly lower thermal absorption cross-section of the mixed moderator increases f . As a result, the hardened spectrum increase the conversion of U238 to plutonium, enabling the reactor to achieve significantly higher fuel burnup [7].

Table I. Comparison of four-factor parameters at fresh fuel under different moderators.

	Pure H ₂ O (Super critical)	1462ppm boron (Critical)	49.5vf% D ₂ O (Critical)
Fast fission factor (ε)	1.37823	1.41220	1.63454
Resonance escape probability (p)	0.59657	0.59662	0.45883
Thermal utilization factor (f)	0.95409	0.84817	0.97239
Reproduction factor (η)	1.39935	1.39919	1.37164
Infinity multiplication factor (k_{∞})	1.09775	0.99990	1.00029

3. COARSE GROUP OPTIMIZATION FOR TWO-STEP ANALYSIS

In the conventional two-step analysis framework for PWRs, fine-group cross-sections are collapsed into two coarse groups using flux-weighted averaging over a single assembly. These collapsed cross-sections are then utilized in subsequent three-dimensional nodal diffusion calculations. However, when a D₂O/H₂O mixed moderator is employed, the resulting neutron spectrum can differ significantly from that of a pure H₂O or a borated H₂O environment. This spectral distortion can lead to substantial errors in the conventional two-group cross-section structure, potentially compromising the accuracy of the nodal diffusion calculations.

Kim et al. [8] proposed an algorithm to optimize the few-group structure tailored to the neutron spectrum of a very high temperature gas-cooled reactor (VHTR) They evaluated cross-section behavior under various conditions, including changes in temperature and burnup. A similar optimization approach can also be applied to the mixed-moderator system, The methodology adopted in this study is described as follows:

- (a) Single assembly simulations were performed using the MCS code for various cases, including different combinations of temperature, burnup, BA configurations, and control rod insertion. The state with a pure H₂O moderator was set as the reference (ref), while states employing either soluble boron control or a D₂O/H₂O mixed moderator were treated as variations (var). These labels (ref and var) are used as indices in the subsequent expressions. Cross-sections and scalar fluxes were tallied using the fine group (190-group) structure for both the reference and variation moderator conditions.
- (b) Taking the first fine group as the coarse group, the cross-sections for the variation state were obtained using the reference spectrum for the coarse group G .

$$\phi_{G,i}^{var} = \sum_{g \in G} \phi_{g,i}^{var}, \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_{G,i}^{ref} = \sum_{g \in G} \phi_{g,i}^{ref}, \quad \Sigma_{aG,i} = \frac{\sum_{g \in G} \Sigma_{ag,i}^{var} \phi_{g,i}^{ref}}{\phi_{G,i}^{ref}}, \quad \nu \Sigma_{fG,i} = \frac{\sum_{g \in G} \nu \Sigma_{fg,i}^{var} \phi_{g,i}^{ref}}{\phi_{G,i}^{ref}}, \quad (3)$$

where g is the fine group index, G is the coarse group index, and i denotes each simulation case index corresponding to different physical and modeling conditions.

- (c) The k_{∞} values for the variation state are evaluated in two ways: (i) exactly, and (ii) using the cross-sections derived by applying the reference spectrum only to coarse group G .

$$k_{\infty,i} = \frac{\sum_g \nu \Sigma_{fg,i}^{var} \phi_{g,i}^{var}}{\sum_g \Sigma_{ag,i}^{var} \phi_{g,i}^{var}}, \quad k'_{\infty,i} = \frac{\sum_{g \notin G} \nu \Sigma_{fg,i}^{var} \phi_{g,i}^{var} + \nu \Sigma_{fG,i} \phi_{G,i}^{var}}{\sum_{g \notin G} \Sigma_{ag,i}^{var} \phi_{g,i}^{var} + \Sigma_{aG,i} \phi_{G,i}^{var}}. \quad (4)$$

- (d) The difference between the two k_{∞} values is the error introduced by adopting the reference spectrum only for the coarse group G . If the maximum difference across all the cases is smaller than a specified criterion, one additional fine group is added to the current coarse group and go to step (b). Otherwise, the current coarse group boundary is fixed, and set the next fine group as the next coarse group and go to step (b).

The overall procedure is illustrated in Figure 4. Table II summarizes the simulation cases used in the energy-group structure optimization. The cases involving changes in the number of BAs employ the assembly configurations shown in Figure 1.

Table II. Cases used for optimizing the energy group structure.

Case	Burnup (MWd/kgU)	Fuel temp. (K)	Coolant temp. (K)	No. of BAs	Control rod
1	0	900	600	20	-
2	15	900	600	20	-
3	35	900	600	20	-
4	0	300	300	20	-
5	0	600	600	20	-
6	0	900	600	16	-
7	0	900	600	24	-
8	0	300	300	20	B ₄ C
9	0	900	600	20	B ₄ C
10	0	300	300	20	Ag-In-Cd
11	0	900	600	20	Ag-In-Cd

Figure 4. Flowchart of the coarse group optimization process implemented with the MCS code.

Table III presents the selected criteria used to collapse the fine-group structure into two-group and eight-group coarse energy structures. These criteria were adjusted iteratively to determine the appropriate group boundaries. For the soluble boron variation, reactivity deviation criteria of 602 pcm and 32 pcm were applied to determine the two-group and eight-group structures, respectively. In contrast, for the D₂O/H₂O mixture case, significantly higher thresholds of 4,044 pcm and 311 pcm were required. This indicates that the use of a two-group structure in the D₂O/H₂O environment is inadequate to preserve accurate reaction rates.

Table III. Criteria for determining two- and eight-group energy structures under different moderator conditions.

No. of groups	Moderator variation	Criteria (pcm) used to define group boundary
2	2000 ppm boron concentration	602
	50% D ₂ O fraction	4,044
8	2000 ppm boron concentration	32
	50% D ₂ O fraction	311

Figure 5 illustrates the number of energy groups and the corresponding group boundaries when the reactivity deviation criteria originally selected for the soluble boron case are applied to the D₂O/H₂O moderator environment. While the soluble boron case yields two-group and eight-group structures under criteria of 602 pcm and 32 pcm, respectively, applying the same criteria to the D₂O/H₂O moderator produces seven-group and 25-group structures to achieve comparable accuracy. Figure 6 presents the differences in k_{∞} under the 32 pcm criterion for the D₂O/H₂O moderator environment, where higher group indices correspond to lower neutron energy ranges.

Figure 5. Energy group boundaries for D₂O/H₂O moderator under reactivity deviation criteria of 602 pcm and 32 pcm.

Figure 6. k_{∞} differences across energy groups for each case under the D₂O/H₂O moderator (32 pcm criterion).

These results indicate that conventional energy group structures are inadequate in the D₂O/H₂O moderator environment, necessitating the use of finer group structures to ensure accurate nodal diffusion calculations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the neutronic characteristics of spectrum shift reactivity control in a soluble boron-free (SBF) small modular reactor (SMR) design using a D₂O/H₂O mixed moderator.

Soluble boron induces slight spectral hardening, primarily due to the high thermal neutron absorption cross-section of boron, which marginally increases the fast fission factor but reduces thermal flux, leading to lower thermal utilization factor relative to the pure H₂O case.

In contrast, the use of a D₂O/H₂O moderator significantly hardens the neutron spectrum compared to both pure H₂O and soluble boron environments. This hardened spectrum leads to an increase in the fast fission factor, while the slightly reduced thermal neutron absorption of D₂O leads to an increase thermal utilization factor, resulting in an extended critical operation period compared to soluble boron case.

Additionally, a coarse energy group optimization method was applied using a modified reference method. Under conditions that produce similar reactivity effects, specifically a 2000 ppm boron concentration in the soluble boron case and a 50% D₂O fraction in the D₂O/H₂O moderator case, the

group structures that provide comparable accuracy in preserving reaction rates to the two-group and eight-group cases in the soluble boron system correspond to approximately seven-group and 25-group structures in the D₂O/H₂O moderator, respectively, due to the harder neutron spectrum. The findings suggest that the use of a conventional energy group structure in the D₂O/H₂O moderator environment does not provide sufficient accuracy, and a finer energy group structure is necessary to ensure accurate nodal diffusion calculations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the Ministry of Science and ICT (MSIT of Korea) (RS-2024-00436693) and Human Resources Program in Energy Technology of the Korea Institute of Energy Technology Evaluation and Planning (KETEP), which was funded by Ministry of Trade, Industry & Energy (MOTIE of Korea) (No. RS-2024-00398425)

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Mars, D. Gans. "Spectral shift control reactor design and economic study." *Office of Technical Services*, **1241** (1961).
- [2] J. Storrer, S. Rigg. "The Vulcain core power experiment." *Proce. 3rd U.N conference peaceful uses atomic energy*, **1**, pp. 337(1964).
- [3] B.A. Lindley, G.T. Parks. "The Spectral Shift Control Reactor as an option for much improved uranium utilisation in single-batch SMRs." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **309**, pp. 75-83 (2016).
- [4] H. O. Kang, B. J. Lee, S. G. Lim. "Light water SMR development status in Korea." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **419**, 112966 (2024).
- [5] J. S. Kang, T. S. Jung, J. Yoon. "Reactor core design with practical gadolinia burnable absorbers for soluble boron-free operation in the innovative SMR." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **56**(8), pp. 3144-3154 (Aug-2024).
- [6] H. Lee, et al. "MCS–A Monte Carlo particle transport code for large-scale power reactor analysis." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **139**, 107276 (2020).
- [7] Y. Ronen, A. Galperin. "A comparison between spectral shift control methods for light water reactors." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **7**, pp. 59-64 (1980).
- [8] K.S. Kim, J.Y. Cho, H.C. Lee, J.M. Noh, S.Q. Zee, "Development of a physics analysis procedure for the prismatic very high temperature gas-cooled reactors.", *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **34**, pp. 849–860 (2007).